

D6.2 First report on Communication and Dissemination activities

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List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
COMRADES	Project Name
WP	Work Package
GOV2U	Government To You
DoA	Description of Action
GA	General Assembly

Executive summary

COMRADES project was launched in January 2016 with a lifetime of 36 months and it aims to empower communities with intelligent socio-technical solutions to help them reconnect, respond to, and recover from crisis situations.

COMRADES consortium will build a next generation, intelligent resilience platform to provide high socio-technical innovation and to support community resilience in crises situations. The platform will capture and process in real-time, multilingual social information streams from distributed communities, for the purpose of identifying, aggregating, and verifying reported events at the citizen and community levels. Resilience frameworks, guidelines and best practices will be embedded into the platform design and functionality, enriched with open datasets and open source software.

The main objectives of the project is to foster social innovation during crises for safeguarding communities during critical scenarios from inaccurate, distrusted, and overhyped information, and for raising citizen and community awareness of crisis situations by providing them with filtered, validated, enriched, high quality, and actionable knowledge. Community decision-making will be assisted by automated methods for real-time, intelligent processing and linking of crowdsourced crisis information.

This document forms deliverable D6.2 *“First report on communication and dissemination activities”*. It outlines the dissemination and communication objectives and strategy of the reporting period and focuses on the tools and activities that were undertaken to accomplish the objectives set. The deliverable reports on dissemination tools (website, social media, press releases, newsletter issues, brochures, etc.) used from M1 to M12 to disseminate the project implementing the online and offline dissemination strategy D6.1 deliverable in M6. Also, it presents the dissemination activities that have been implemented by the partners and are foreseen in the Description of Action for WP6. It will be updated yearly during the whole du project.

It is based on, and is consistent with, the DoA and the CA, but is not a substitute for reading these documents.

Introduction

Collective intelligence and social innovation platforms are set to play an important role in supporting and boosting community resilience, by providing the means for communities to acquire valued information, to help them self-assess, make informed decisions, communicate, and organize their response. Moreover, social media has emerged in recent years as a dominant channel for communities to gather and spread information during crises.

The project's stance to improve resilience can therefore be summarized by:

- (1) **Continuously** enhancing community resilience through ICT, instead of focusing on specific shocks or disruptive events.
- (2) Enabling a broad range of actors to acquire a **relevant, consistent** and **coherent** understanding of a stressing situation.
- (3) **Empower** decision makers and trigger community engagement on response and recovery efforts, including long-term mitigation and preparation.

The project's platform will assist in safeguarding communities during critical scenarios from inaccurate, distrusted, and overhyped information, and for raising citizen and community awareness of crisis situations by providing them with filtered, validated, enriched, high quality, and actionable knowledge.

This document is the second deliverable of WP6 and is aimed at reporting on the progress made in using project dissemination tools in order to implement the communication strategy of the project.

The dissemination and communication strategy that was described in the D6.1 document presented a clear way to address the project's stakeholders and how it will offer the various identified target groups incentive to take action, get involved, and promote the project. It was developed with the purpose of:

- raising awareness about COMRADES project,
- fostering a clear understanding of WP6 dissemination and communications objectives and how they will be implemented in the context of the project's objectives,
- outlining how COMRADES partners will be involved in WP6, their roles and responsibilities.

As described in the DoA, all partners are responsible for individual dissemination tasks, for example, authorship of research publications, attendance of conferences and events, etc. However, Gov2U is the leader of the WP, and the coordinator of communication actions with substantial strategic input from all partners, therefore any communication activities shall be widely coordinated and discussed within the consortium.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to present a yearly report related to project by the consortium members. The current deliverable outlines the dissemination and communication objectives and strategy of the reporting period and focuses on the tools and activities that were undertaken to accomplish these dissemination tools (website, social media, press releases, newsletter issues, brochures, etc.) used from M1 to M12 to disseminate the project,

implementing the online and offline dissemination strategy set with activities that have been implemented by the consortium and are foreseen in the Description of Action for WP6.

1.2 Methodology of the deliverable

The methodology followed for the production of the current deliverable is based on the constructive and close collaboration of WP6 leader with the WP6 partners.

The initial version of the D6.2 “The first report on Communication and Dissemination activities” was compiled by Gov2u and was sent to WP6 partners for reviewing and commenting. The current deliverable was finalized after incorporating WP6 partner’s comments/suggestions and sent to the project leader.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable addresses three main aspects of the dissemination of the project. The first section serves as an introduction of the project and WP6 and the deliverable to the readers. The second section provides a summary of objectives and the strategy followed during the reporting period.

Finally, the third section focuses on the dissemination and communication tools used and activities implemented for the achievement of the objectives set for this period. The concluding remarks highlights the main points and issues presented in the report.

1.4 Intended audience

This deliverable is addressed to:

<i>Group of readers</i>	<i>Reasons for reading</i>
Comrades consortium partners	To be informed about the dissemination activities during the reporting period (M1-M12)
Target groups: general public, scientific community, potential new end-users, possible dissemination partners, project stakeholders	To be informed about dissemination activities performed within the reporting period and raise awareness about the project, announce project objectives, keep track of communication progress and further develop community interest
Representatives of organization and institutions involved in similar projects or initiatives.	To share knowledge, information and best practices that can be adopted and utilized in similar projects
European Commission	This document is a deliverable of the Comrades project

Table 1 : Intended audience

1.5 Relation of the deliverable to WP6 deliverables

The current deliverable is interrelated with other deliverables of WP6. The list below explains the dependencies and relation:

- **D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan**, that set the communication and dissemination strategy, identified stakeholder groups and envisaged the tools to be used.
- **D6.3, D6.6 Initial Exploitation plan and Final Exploitation Plan (M18 and M36)**: These deliverables are dedicated to the project exploitation actions, in other words, the strategy of the project as a business product and model in the relevant market, identifying the needed actions and target audiences to attract. The exploitation actions will build upon the communication actions (WP6), innovation actions (WP5) and research actions to the extent of community engagement (WP2).
- **D6.4, D6.5 Report on dissemination activities (M24, M36)**: These deliverables will be produced annually and will be focused on the reporting of dissemination activities carried out by Gov2U and all partners in the specific reporting period. These reports will include the progress made on the action plan and activities that are foreseen in the current deliverable as well.

1.6 Quality management

For ensuring the quality of the current document, the first ideas were presented and discussed during the Kick off meeting of the COMRADES project, as well as in teleconferences that were regularly conducted.

The project partner GOV2U, prepared the initial draft of the current document and distributed it to WP6 partners for reviewing and contribution. This deliverable uses the official template of the project and language quality control has been performed.

2 Communication and Dissemination objectives for the reporting period

This section presents in detail the dissemination and communication objectives and strategy implemented for this reporting. In this period, WP6 focused its efforts on developing dissemination and communication strategy and activities that will result to the best and most effective promotion of the project at local level, European and international levels. During this year WP6 organised itself internally and define roles and responsibilities for each WP6 partner. It was clear from the early first month of the project that each partner markets the project and all WP6 partners need to contribute to dissemination and undertake correspondence facilitate the internal communication and effective coordination of partners.

The main objectives of WP6 for the reporting period were the following:

- Design and launch the Comrades website;
- Design and create the promotional material of the project (logo, general presentation, newsletter template, project brochure, project factsheet, poster, social media accounts);
- Create the design and the content of promotional materials (project brochure, project factsheet, project newsletter);
- Identify and organize the stakeholders' groups;
- Coordinate with partners for their better engagement in communication and stronger involvement in dissemination action;
- Participation in events at national, European and international level to raise the awareness and the visibility for the project;
- Establish, maintain and enhance collaboration with other EU funded projects in the same domain, especially with other CAPS projects in particular;
- Provide the deliverables and reports corresponding to the reporting period M1-M12;
- Establish and maintain mechanisms for effective and timely internal and external communication.

3 Dissemination and Communication tools and activities

An overview of the dissemination tools and activities created and performed by the Comrades partners in order to raise the visibility of the project is being provided in this chapter.

Dissemination tools are in a way different formats and channels that are being used to transmit important messages, while the activities are the concrete actions by which these tools could be possibly be implemented.

3.1 Comrades logo, general presentation, templates

The project identity is a very important subset of the communication action, therefore project logo (in 3 versions) as well as the general presentation and templates of the deliverables were created during M1 and shared with the partners for consortium use.

Figure 1 : Comrades logo

3.2 Comrades website

Comrades website was created in M3 of the project. The projects website is a major means of information for communication with the visitors and thus it is harmonized and interrelated with the main goals of the WP6 to disseminate the project concept, goals as well as findings, as well as to engage key stakeholders for knowledge sharing, as well as engage with communities undergoing resilience challenges to feed the research purposes of the project.

Comrades website was being developed in consideration that it is a versatile and a resourceful dissemination tool. It is necessary since the information pertaining to the project is included for all audiences. Since its launch, it is regularly being updated so that the number of returning visitors would grow. Updates refer to the project news, relevant articles, newsletter issues other activities dedicated to dissemination. The update of the website content, layout and design is ongoing throughout the implementation of the project.

Figure 2 : Comrades website

Data retrieved from the backend of Comrades website show the following information:

<i>Field</i>	<i>Data</i>
Returning visitors	40 %
Website views per month on average	1467
Number of items of Project news	13

Table 2 : Comrades website statistics

Data retrieved from Google Analytics¹ as of April 2016 through the end of the year indicate that the website generated **17 742 Page views**, had **2010 sessions** and **1214 unique visitors**.

<i>Field</i>	<i>Data</i>
Unique visitors	1214
Number of page views	17742
Percentage of New visits	60.4 %
Number of Returning visits	39.6 %
Pages viewed per session	5.8

Table 3 : Comrades website data from Google analytics

¹ The full report of Google analytics is included in Appendix I.

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Furthermore, a number of activities related to the website were performed during the reporting period:

- Queries, expressions of interest and requests with reference to the project are received through the website proving interest for Comrades. Responses and/or actions to emails and inquiries are provided by
- Promotional materials such as brochure, poster, factsheet, etc. are uploaded in the public website and partners' repository.

3.3 Social Media accounts

Social media profiles play a promotional role for the project a wide range of audience. Constant posts and updates of status on social media profiles on the projects developments, news and sharing of best practices increase the engagement of the interested audience and help to achieve interaction with the users. This is of particular importance to this project as it is related to community innovation, so the attraction of very specific audiences is vital.

Social media proves to be the most effective dissemination tool due to the popularity, ease of access and rapid information flow. Thus social media accounts allow the project to employ them to create an even wider community of interest and disseminate news, activities and developments.

The project social media profiles were created on Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn, the links to these accounts were integrated into the project website and made visible, as well as additional feed flow is being shown on the project website, additionally inviting user to slide and/or click and follow the interesting topics posted on Comrades social media (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 : Social media integration on Comrades website

The following tables below show the status of the social media accounts and related statistics:

Field	Details
Social media	Facebook
Project Month	December 2016
URL	https://www.facebook.com/comradesproject/

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Status	Likes 37
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Table 4 : Comrades Facebook status

Field	Details
Social media	Twitter
Project Month	December 2016
URL	https://twitter.com/comradesproject
Status	613 Tweets, 219 Followers, 539 Likes

Table 5 : Comrades Twitter status

It is important to mention, that Comrades profile has managed to gather a very specific audience on Twitter account, with the absolute majority of followers coming from the fields of Technology, Business, Entrepreneurship and Policy.²

Field	Details
Social media	LinkedIn
Project Month	December 2016
URL	https://be.linkedin.com/in/comradesproject
Status	68 Connections

Table 6 : Comrades LinkedIn status

3.4 Newsletter

As already mentioned in D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan (M6), the project newsletters are used to announce the project, develop a profile, give regular updates on its progress and developments and achieve buy-in and take-up of its solution after the completion of are creative dissemination tools addressing them to know that the project is a success.

During the reporting period (M1-M12) the Comrades has published 1 Newsletter (July 2016) announcing project activities and developments during the first months of the project. It was decided between the consortium partners, that the Newsletter shall be one of the main direct communication channels, and therefore it has to be issued corresponding the internal activity frequency the project, in order to avoid spamming target audiences with little content.

² Please see Appendix 2 for full Twitter analysis data.

The structure of Newsletter consists of the following standard sections: “Editorial”, “Community”, “Technology”, “Project News”, “Events” and “Interesting reads”.

The Newsletter is accessible through “News”> “Newsletter” section on the website (<http://www.comrades-project.eu/news/newsletter.html>), as well as there are 3 link buttons “Subscribe”, placed in 3 different subpages of the website.

The next issue of the Newsletter will be released together with Press release at the beginning of 2017 and will be focused on the research activities by the project partners, presenting success stories from community workshops organized within WP2.

Field	Details
Dissemination tools	Newsletter 1
Project Month	July 2016
URL	http://www.comrades-project.eu/news/newsletter.html
Status	Distributed to Stakeholders list (100+ contacts), 18 Subscribers on website

Table 7 : Comrades Newsletter

3.5 Promotional materials

Promoting materials (brochure, factsheet, general presentation) are a collection of dissemination and promotional tools that are used to raise awareness and visibility of the project, to attract and motivate stakeholders and to be distributed at project presentations in events and conferences by the project partners.

General Objective

The **COMRADES** project works with local partners to create an **open-source**, community resilience platform.

What's in it for me?

Support to set up and use a platform which uses **cutting edge technology** for helping citizens to get a consistent, coherent understanding of the events around them in **real time** and to **exchange intelligence** when their community is severely hit by natural disasters such as **floods, earthquakes, and hurricanes**.

Information will be gathered via multiple channels such as **social media, text messaging, and various other channels** by the **COMRADES platform**. A **crisis map** will be created where citizens can view and share information about the crisis, to increase their **resilience and situational awareness**.

COMRADES goes beyond the mere gathering of information, by assisting communities in getting **self-organized** for more efficient response to, and recover from crisis. The platform keeps the **citizens well connected during emergencies**, and matches those in need of help with fellow citizens who can provide the requested assistance.

Who is involved?

COMRADES will engage with **three types** of specific communities that are core to effective resilience efforts:

- ✓ **Activists** (platform deployers): individuals and groups of people who set up instances of the **Ushahidi platform**;
- ✓ **Responders**: communities that organise and coordinate resources and provide expertise when the Ushahidi platform is deployed;
- ✓ **Reporters**: communities who report on crisis.

Specific Objectives

- ✓ To automatically **identify, process, assess, and monitor** emergency events;
- ✓ To measure the **informativeness and validity** of crisis information;
- ✓ To **develop** the intelligent **COMRADES platform** for community resilience;
- ✓ To deploy **COMRADES** to **support local communities** and **digital responders** in the response to and recovery from crises;
- ✓ To **support and foster** community resilience as a **continuous process**.

How will it work?

The functions that **COMRADES** platform plans to include are:

- ✓ Quickly filtering citizens' reports as they arrive from **social media** and **mobile texts**;
- ✓ **Removing uninformative and irrelevant ones**;
- ✓ **Identifying unreliable sources**;
- ✓ **Picks up, and alerts** to several lone messages requesting urgent help during a crisis;
- ✓ **Extracts, groups, and monitors** unfolding emergency micro-events.

How to be involved?

The **COMRADES project** will actively approach different communities and citizens from around the globe by involving them at **two levels**:

Co-Creation: Engage **multiple communities** in the **requirements, design, and evaluation tasks**;

Use: Promote and support the deployment and use of the platform to **empower citizens and communities** to improve their resilience.

*The platform will be based on **Ushahidi** solution: a common platform for crisis mapping, developed in collaboration with **iHub**.*

Figure 4 : Comrades brochure

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During the reporting period, a brochure and a factsheet have been created and are available on the website in order to be circulated, as well as general presentation provided for the use of partners. The poster of the project will be issued at the beginning of 2017 to suit the rising events participation activity among the project partners and intensified end user engagements activities within WP2.

4 Communication and dissemination activities

The following sections outline the dissemination activities carried out during this reporting period:

4.1 Participation in events

<i>Partner</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Description of event</i>	<i>Results and outcomes</i>
University of Sheffield, UK	September, 2016	Big Data and Analytics Summer School	http://www.essex.ac.uk/iads/events/summer-school.aspx	Diana Maynard presented a tutorial on NLP and Social Media Analysis
University of Sheffield, UK	November, 2016	PEARS workshop in Cambridge, UK	http://www.cl.cam.ac.uk/~aac10/O_Sworkshop.html	Diana Maynard gave an invited talk about Text mining applications with GATE
University of Sheffield, UK	November, 2016	Annual Symposium at the Grantham Centre for Sustainable Futures / Sheffield Institute for International Development	http://grantham.sheffield.ac.uk/symposium2016/	Active attendance by Diana Maynard
Open University, UK	September, 2016	CAPSSI Community Workshop in Bratislava	https://capssi.eu/event/capssi-community-workshop/?instance_id=17	Lara Piccolo presented the main Comrades project challenges and objectives
Open University, UK	August, 2016	IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining in USA	http://asonam.cpsc.ucalgary.ca/2016/	Active attendance by Harith Alani
Open University, UK	October, 2016	International Semantic Web Conference, Kobe, Japan	http://iswc2016.semanticweb.org	Active attendance by Harith Alani and Gregoire Burel
University of Agder	June, 2016	Workshop on Resilience in Delft, Netherlands	http://www.tudelft.nl/nl/onderzoek/thematische-samenwerking/delft-research-	Tina Comes gave a presentation on "How can ICT

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			based-initiatives/delft-deltas-infrastructures-mobility-initiative/dimi-events/how-can-resilient-infrastructures-contribute-to-social-justice/	and information systems contribute to resilience?”, to be found here
University of Agder	October, 2016	Annual conference for municipalities on event safety	http://gemeentenucongressen.nl/evenementenveiligheid/programma.html	Kenny Meesters gave a presentation ‘Directing the online dynamics of empowered citizens’
University of Agder	September, 2016	Triplex 2016, international humanitarian exercise in Norway	https://www.etcluster.org/event/triplex-2016	Kenny Meesters and Bjørn Erik Munkvold presented COMRADES to practitioners

Table 8 : Attended events

4.2 Publications (accepted/submitted/presented to the conference proceedings and scientific journals)

No	Field	Details
1.	Title of publication	<i>Designing for Networked Community Resilience</i>
	Date of publication	May, 2016
	Name of Author(s)	Prof. Tina Comes
	Journal, Publishing house	Humanitarian Technology: Science, Systems and Global Impact 2016, HumTech2016, 7-9 June 2016, Massachusetts, USA
	Online link	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/301168128_Designing_for_Networked_Community_Resilience
2.	Title of publication	<i>Making Sense of Crises: The Implications of Information Asymmetries for Resilience and Social Justice in Disaster-ridden Communities</i>
	Date of publication	Currently under review, TBD

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	Name of Author(s)	Tina Comes, Kenny Meesters and Stina Torjesen (University of Agder)
	Journal, Publishing house	Sustainable and Resilient Infrastructure
3.	Title of publication	<i>Natural Language Processing for the Semantic Web</i>
	Date of publication	2017
	Name of Author(s)	Diana Maynard, Kalina Bontcheva, Isabelle Augenstein
	Journal, Publishing house	Morgan Claypool

Table 9 : Submitted Publications

4.3 Partner websites

The interlinking is a very good way to generate more traffic to the website. The following table shows the description of the project with adequate links to the Comrades website on the consortium partners' websites:

<i>Partner</i>	<i>Website link</i>
Open University, UK	http://kmi.open.ac.uk/projects/name/comrades
University of Sheffield, UK	https://gate.ac.uk/projects/comrades/index.html
University of Agder	http://ciem.uia.no/project/comrades

Table 10 : Links to Comrades on partner websites

4.4 Liaison with other projects, networks and initiatives

Effective networking is about building strong and useful relationships and liaisons over time that can lead to mutual understanding, trust, synergies, acceptance and benefits with similar EU projects and other networks. Such liaisons and networks can help in our effort to raise the project's positive reputation and take-up its solution in the long term.

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Early on in this reporting period, a serious effort began to contact domain area, in order to create synergies that would be proven helpful for both sides. Comrades have started engaging with other similar projects and creating an active list of contacts, i.e., forwarding Newsletter and actively engaging on social media accounts.

Following Gov2U initiative, it has also been agreed with FLOOD-serv to proceed in collaboration for further synergies in cross dissemination activities.

Comrades Newsletter was also featured on [CAPPSI Newsletter](#), designed for CAPS community projects, what certainly enhanced the visibility of Comrades project and open up collaboration channels.

5 Dissemination activities for Year2

Entering the second year of the project the dissemination of the project

4.1 Dissemination and communication tools

4.1.1 Comrades website

- Continuous update of information, layout, design (ongoing);
- Updating project website with content such as: news articles on project progress, Comrades articles in the press, events, project press releases, project promotional material etc. (ongoing).

4.1.2 Comrades social media

- Continuous update of the project's social networks profiles with news on the project developments, with news from other related thematic areas, with promotional material or other items related to the dissemination.
- Continuous networking via social media profiles in order to broaden the community of interest.

4.1.3 Newsletter

The next issue of the newsletter will be published at the beginning of 2017.

The objective of WP6 is to keep publishing a newsletter at least twice a year, meaning that there will be another 2 issues of the project newsletter in 2017.

4.1.4 Collaboration with other CAPS and similar projects

The project will further collaborate with other similar projects, especially CAPS community. This activity will further assist projects to collect and consolidate scientific results and disseminate project developments and results. For the following project period, and in establishing a more coherent cooperation with projects we have already identified as similar.

Collaboration will be implemented via:

- Networking;
- Affiliate marketing between the projects, creating linkages and references, publishing project briefs and news articles regarding the project and its developments via collaborators' websites;
- Exchange of information and knowledge via emailing informing them about project's latest developments;
- The organization of common events.

4.1.5 Participation in events

In the second year of the project, Comrades partners will keep on participating in conferences within the European Union that are considered to be of strategic interest.

Moreover, consortium partners have already planned to participate at the following events:

- The European Semantic Web Conference, <http://2017.eswc-conferences.org/>, May 2017, Portoroz, Slovenia by Harith Alani (Open University) and Diana Maynard (University of Sheffield);
- ISCRAM 2017, <https://iscram2017.mines-albi.fr/> by Kenny Meesters and Tina Comes attending / presenting;
- Resilience Week 2016, <http://www.2016resilienceweek.org> by Shadrock Roberts (iHub).

6 Conclusion

According to Comrades DoA, the principal objective of this deliverable was to present the dissemination tools and activities results for the first reporting period M1-M12. Therefore, the main part of carried out by the partners during the presented the dissemination tools prepared or updated according the project progress.

Secondly, the document provides (publications, events, other dissemination activities during the reporting period. The actions carried out by the partners were diversified, reaching from prep releases, publishing project related information on other websites, placing special effort on liaising with other CAPS projects, related events. Furthermore, the deliverable presented actions that will be continued in the next reporting period.

APPENDIX I: Google analytics report for Comrades website

APPENDIX II: Twitter analysis data

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